

Can tree-structured classifiers add value to the investor?

Abstract

We analyse the investor welfare gain of including tree-structured classifiers' predictions about the relative performance of stock vs. cash. The CART, bagging, and random-forest methods select the VIX level and momentum, the earning bond yield level and momentum, and the detrended risk-free rate as the most important state variables to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash out-of-sample. These tree-structured classifiers' predictions are used as a binary state variable to estimate optimal investor portfolios that also deliver out-of-sample higher Sharpe ratios and certainty equivalent return gains than competing portfolio strategies that exclude them.

Key Words: Market timing; Tree-structured classifiers; State variables; Performance evaluation.

JEL Classification: G11, G19.

1. Introduction

The upsurge of passive investing is a clear trend in financial markets that reinforces the concerns about active fund managers. Fund managers may not charge fees according to their added value (Gil-Bazo & Verdú, 2009), and there is mixed evidence of the persistence of funds' performance (see Carhart, 1997; Ferreira, Keswani, Miguel, & Ramos, 2012; Hendricks, Patel, & Zeckhauser, 1993; Kacperczyk, van Nieuwerburgh, & Veldkamp, 2014). Therefore, there is no clear evidence of the existence of skilled or informed mutual fund managers.

The classical approach to investors' asset allocation problem requires the modelling of the underlying assets' return distribution and then the plugging of the estimated parameter values into an analytical or numerical solution to the problem defined over an objective function. There is an enormous literature on return predictability that tries to determine the factors that anticipate the dynamics of the underlying assets' return distribution,¹ which can be used to allocate investors' wealth optimally to different assets depending on the perceived signal of their relative attractiveness. However, the empirical evidence also shows a clear difficulty in delivering consistently superior out-of-sample forecasts of the associated models relative to a simple forecast based on the historical average (Goyal & Welch, 2008); consequently, these models may not help investors to time the market. The existence of non-linearities and structural breaks in the relationship between the state variables and the asset returns (Fransens & Dijk, 2000) as well as the stylized behaviour of financial asset returns, such as negative skewness, fat tails, and volatility clustering (Cont, 2001), make the activity of investing a delicate task.

In this paper we study the ability of tree-structured classifiers and regression tree classifiers (CART hereafter) to help investors to engage a profitable investment strategy in-sample and especially out-of-sample. The high level of complexity of financial markets makes the use of these classifiers particularly suitable, as they can handle problems characterized by high dimensionality, non-normality, and non-homogeneity, that is, different relationships between variables in different parts of the measurement space (Breiman, Friedman, Olshen, & Stone, 1984). Thus, the tree-structured classification not only is used to produce an accurate classifier but also can be used to

¹ See, among others, Ang and Bekaert (2007); Baker and Wurgler (2006); Campbell (1991); Cochrane and Piazzesi (2005); Fama and French (1988, 1989); Fama and Schwert (1977); Ferreira and Santa Clara (2011); Lettau and Ludvigson (2001); Ludvigson and Ng (2009); and Maio (2013).

identify the most important variables and their interactions or to uncover the predictive structure of any problem, especially in a non-linear context. Therefore, we can summarize the advantages of the CART over other existing methodologies for forecasting, especially the linear parametric ones, as follows: 1) it is a non-parametric technique that does not require specification of the underlying distribution of the variables being modelled, 2) it does not require variables to be selected in advance, as the CART algorithm will identify the most significant variables and eliminate the non-significant ones itself,² 3) the CART can easily handle outliers, noisy data, and especially non-normality that is related to the negative skewness and fat tails of financial asset return distribution, and 4) CART results are intuitive and very easily interpreted, especially compared with other plausible non-parametric techniques such as the neural networks considered as ‘black-box’ methods.³ The main disadvantages of the CART methodology are that it may have unstable decision trees and that insignificant modifications of the learning sample could lead to radical changes in splitting variables and values. To address these problems, we explore more complex alternatives to the CART approach by growing an ensemble of trees and letting them vote for the most popular class. We consider the bagging (Breiman, 1996a and b) and random-forest (Breiman, 2001) methodologies to try to increase the accuracy of the resulting predictions and to handle the instability issue. Due to the increasing complexity of the proposed methods, we try to assess their relevance to our asset allocation context particularly compared with simpler strategies, such as the linear parametric or the passive out-of-sample strategy.

Tree-structured classifiers are used especially in the credit risk literature to analyse different problems, such as the classification of financially distressed firms (Frydman, Altman, & Kao, 1985) or corporate credit rating changes (Jones, Johnstone, & Wilson, 2015), and to a lesser extent in the asset allocation context (see Sorensen, Miller, & Ooi, 2000).

An important contribution of our paper is to show how to integrate the CART prediction easily into an asset allocation problem by considering a new binary state variable that takes the value one if the S&P 500 outperforms the cash and zero

² Alternatively, it could be considered a shortcoming not to be able to force the use of variables in the model.

³ Zhang, Patuwo, and Hu (1998) outline different limitations of artificial neural networks: they are black-box methods with no explicit relationship form to explain and analyse the relationship between inputs and outputs, prone to overfitting problems, and time consuming.

otherwise. Our methodology involves two steps. First, we use the classification and regression tree classifier (CART hereafter) to establish the relationship between our binary dependent variable, which takes the value one if the S&P 500 outperforms the cash and zero otherwise, and a list of potential predictors of the excess stock return. Second, we use the CART prediction in a portfolio context that consists of an investor who optimally invests her/his wealth among stocks and the Treasury bill rate. We consider the CART prediction as a new binary state variable that tries to capture the attractiveness of the stock market vs. cash. We try to uncover the usefulness of the information embedded in the CART predictions to add value to the investor. For comparison we compare the ability of the CART predictions to add value to the optimal portfolio formed by investors who only consider the same state variables selected by the tree-structured classifier. To obtain the set of optimal weights, we operate in an optimal asset allocation setting that follows the literature (see Ait-Sahalia & Brandt, 2001; Brandt, 1999; Brandt, Santa Clara, & Valkanov, 2009; and more recently Barroso & Santa-Clara, 2015). We directly estimate the linear relationship between the state variables and the optimal portfolio allocation to the stock market and consider a CRRA utility function. We focus on the added value to the investors produced by the tree-structured classifiers, using different metrics to measure the portfolios' economic performance, such as the main descriptive statistics of the optimal excess portfolio return distribution, the annualized Sharpe ratio, and the certainty equivalent return gain.

From a practical standpoint, our paper provides several useful insights. Firstly, the proposed methodology based on the new binary state variable provided by the CART adds value out-of-sample to the investor, who could operate alternatively using the passive strategy or the linear parametric portfolio rules based on the isolated state variables. Therefore, our binary state variable would subsume the information embedded in the relevant state variables considered in a linear portfolio rule, as it seems to capture adequately the non-linear relationship between them. Secondly, the consideration of bagging and the random forest does not necessarily lead to an increase in the investor welfare. Our out-of-sample results show that the accuracy of the predictions related to the outperformance of the stock market vs. cash based on the binary classifiers is about a remarkable 70%. In our out-of-sample period, neither the bagging nor the random forest method can increase significantly the accuracy attained by the CART predictions, despite their greater complexity. We interpret this result as a signal of the CART's outcome stability. Obviously, this result depends on our sample

and is confirmed by the fact that the CART algorithm mainly chooses the same state variables to predict the excess stock return out-of-sample. The bagging and random-forest variable importance measures' analysis out-of-sample also consistently leads to a ranking of predictors that is similar to the CART algorithm, which we interpret as an indicator of stability. Therefore, our empirical analysis reveals that the consideration of more sophisticated models does not always lead to investor welfare gains. Thirdly, all the tree-structured classifiers emphasize the importance of the VIX level and momentum, the earning yield bond yield (EYBY hereafter) level and momentum, and the detrended risk-free rate to anticipate the behaviour of the stock market among a list of well-known predictors. Thus, a good model to time the market should include the level and dynamics of the state variables related to the investor fear gauge or the market sentiment, captured by the VIX, a measure of the relative stock market valuation dynamics, reflected by the EYBY, and a measure of the interest rate dynamics, the detrended risk-free rate. Our results confirm that the optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is positively and very significantly related to the new binary state variables considered separately and in isolation, I_{CART} , $I_{Bagging}$, and $I_{Random Forest}$. In the presence of the binary state variables, which are a composite model of the potential predictors of the excess stock return, our optimal estimated portfolios show that the last ones are no longer significant in-sample and out-of-sample. The source of this result is based on the CART's ability to capture non-normality and non-homogeneity in the measurement space. The investor welfare gain of investing according to the signal provided by these new binary state variables is particularly significant in terms of the Sharpe ratio and certainty equivalent return increases even out-of-sample.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the methodology. Section 3 presents the data used in the empirical application and the empirical results. Section 4 concludes.

2. Methodological background

This section describes the two-step methodology that we follow to derive the optimal portfolio strategy. First we briefly describe the binary classifiers considered in this paper: the CART, bagging, and the random forest. These tree-structured classifiers are used to predict the outperformance of the stock market vs. cash using a list of state variables that are potential predictors of the excess stock return. The tree-structured

classifiers' predictions provide us with a new binary state variable that takes the value one if the S&P 500 is expected to outperform the cash and zero otherwise. This new state variable can be considered as a combination of the information embedded in the list of potential predictors of the excess stock return. Second, we build on the recent literature by Ait-Sahalia and Brandt (2001), Brandt (1999), and Brandt et al. (2009) and propose portfolios with optimal weights determined by linear functions of the binary classifiers' predictions regarding the outperformance of the stock market vs. cash and the relevant state variables considered by these classifiers. Finally, we mention the measures used to test the added economic value of the binary classifiers' prediction following an asset allocation approach.

2.1 CART, bagging, and the random forest. Predicting the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash

A binary classifier is a rule that assigns a predicted class membership of $C=\{0,1\}$, which represents the set of classes, based on a measurement vector x in the measurement space X . Thus, given any x in X , the rule assigns one of the classes $\{0,1\}$ to x . In our setting we want to predict a binary variable Y_{t+1} in period $t+1$ (=1 if the S&P 500 outperforms cash and 0 otherwise) from the observed state variables vector in period t , $X_t=[X_{1t}, \dots, X_{nt}]$ by growing a binary tree that separates the observations in a binary and sequential fashion. We consider a state variables vector to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash by following the literature on stock return predictability. We consider the level of the following state variables and the corresponding momentum defined as the difference between the variable level and the average variable level over the three previous months:

- interest rate variables: the detrended risk-free rate (Campbell, 1991), the term spread, measured as the ratio between the ten-year government bond yield and the three-month Treasury bill rate (Fama & French, 1989), and the default spread or U.S. credit spread, defined as the yield difference between Moody's Baa-rated and Moody's Aaa-rated corporate bonds (Fama & French, 1989);
- stock market valuation variables: the Robert Shiller price to earnings ratio (PER) and the Robert Shiller EYBY (Maio, 2013);

- market risk aversion and liquidity variables: VIX⁴ or the ‘fear gauge’ (Whaley, 2000) and the U.S. Ted spread, TED, measured as the difference between the three-month U.S. LIBOR interbank market interest rate and the three-month U.S. Treasury bill rate, which is related to funding illiquidity⁵ (Brunnermeier, 2009);
- commodity market variables: the three-month CRB industrial commodity index return and the three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation (Driesprong, Jacobsen, & Benjamin, 2008).

Thus, the number of state variables considered to create our binary trees is 18. The tree-structured classifiers are constructed by repeated splits of subsets of X into two descendant subsets, beginning with X itself. The tree is made of nodes and branches, with nodes being designated as an internal node, which splits into two children, or a terminal node, which does not have any children. A terminal node has a class label associated with it according to the highest posterior probability, such that observations that fall into the particular final node are assigned to that class. The splitting conditions for each node are expressed as an ‘if–then–else’ rule that is determined by a specific splitting criterion so that the data in each of the descendant subsets are purer. Some steps need to be followed to create a tree classifier (Breiman et al., 1984): 1) growing an overly large tree that gives us optimal splits for the tree: to grow a tree at a given node, we search for the best split in terms of decreasing the node impurity using the Gini diversity measure searching through all the state variables; 2) pruning the large tree using a minimal cost complexity criterion to create a sequence of sub-trees to avoid the overfitting of the large tree; and 3) choosing the ‘right tree’ using cross-validation or an independent tree. We choose the best tree based on the misclassification rate estimated by cross-validation using ten cross-validation subsamples.⁶ Once we have the right tree, we assign the class labels and can compute the corresponding misclassification rate.

To improve the stability and predictive power of classification and regression trees, several methods that involve different ways of combining ensembles of classifiers have been developed. These methods result from growing an ensemble of trees and

⁴ Bollerslev, Tauchen, and Zhou (2009) show that an estimate of the variance premium measured as the difference between the VIX^2 and the realized variance predicts stock returns.

⁵ Pastor and Stambaugh (2003) find that marketwide liquidity is a state variable that is important for asset pricing, and Chordia and Subrahmanyam (2001) analyse the relation between the expected equity returns and the level as well as the volatility of trading activity, a proxy for liquidity.

⁶ Alternatively, the best tree can be chosen based on the misclassification rate estimated using an independent test sample.

letting them vote for the most popular class in the classification setting. We consider the bagging (Breiman, 1996a, 1996b) and random-forest (Breiman, 2001) methods. Using bagging we find B replicates randomly selected from the original data set with replacement, and we construct the classifier using each bootstrap sample, resulting in B classifiers. Given a new observation x , we find the class predicted using the majority vote; therefore, for each of the B bootstrap classifiers, the observation x is classified, and finally we assign the class label that is predicted most often among the bootstrap classifiers (Breiman, 1996a, 1996b). Bagging works best when a classifier is unstable, and a small change in the learning set or the classification parameters produces a large change in the classifier (Breiman, 1996a), so perturbing the data considered to create the ensemble of trees can cause significant changes in the predictor constructed. Random forests (Breiman, 2001) are a combination of tree predictors such that each tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently and with the same distribution for all the trees in the forest. Random forests try to improve on bagging by decorrelating the trees. To classify a new observation x , we again use the majority vote from the forest. In our application we choose $B=200$,⁷ and the number of variables considered by the random forest equals $18^{1/2}$.

We create three new binary state variables: 1) $I_{CART,t}$, which takes the value one if the CART predicts that the S&P 500 will outperform the cash and zero otherwise, 2) $I_{Bagging,t}$, which takes the value one if the bagging method predicts that the S&P 500 will outperform the cash and zero otherwise, and 3) $I_{Random\ forest,t}$, which takes the value one if the random-forest method predicts that the S&P 500 will outperform the cash and zero otherwise.

2.2 Using binary classifiers to add value to the investor: An asset allocation approach

This section presents the problem of an investor who needs to allocate her/his wealth between a risk-free asset with return r_f^t and the stock market represented by the S&P 500 with excess return R_{t+1} . The optimal portfolio weight $\alpha_{S\&P500,t}$ allocated to the stock market is defined as a linear function of all the state variables that are expected to have predictive power for describing the dynamics of the stock market and potentially affect

⁷ Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2001) show that an appreciable amount of additional improvement can occur if B is increased from 50 to 100, and the misclassification rate remains constant for all the choices of B greater than or equal to 100. Thus, our choice of B is a conservative one.

investors' expected marginal utility; see for example Brandt (1999). These variables are related by the following portfolio return specification:

$$R_{p,t+1} = r_{f,t} + \alpha_{S\&P500,t} R_{t+1}. \quad (1)$$

The case $\alpha_{S\&P500,t}=1$ corresponds to the passive strategy given by going long in the S&P 500 during that period. We also consider a less risk-averse passive strategy, $\alpha_{S\&P500,t}=0,6$.

The optimal portfolio weight $\alpha_{S\&P500,t}$ is defined as a linear function of the state variables, Z_t :

$$\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha(Z_t; \beta) = Z_t' \beta, \quad (2)$$

with beta being a vector of coefficients to be selected optimally. The investor's optimal asset allocation problem is to maximize her/his expected utility conditional on the sigma algebra determined by the available information set. This problem is mathematically stated as

$$\text{Max}_{\beta} E \left[U \left(R_{p,t+1}(\alpha(Z_t; \beta)) \right) \middle| \Omega_t \right], \quad (3)$$

with $U(R_{p,t+1}; \beta)$ denoting the investor's utility, Ω_t the corresponding sigma algebra, and $E[\bullet | \Omega_t]$ the mathematical expectation conditional on Ω_t . The first-order conditions of this maximization problem are

$$E \left[U' \left(R_{p,t+1}(\alpha(Z_t; \beta)) \right) R_{t+1} \middle| \Omega_t \right] = 0, \quad (4)$$

with $U' \left(R_{p,t+1}; \beta \right)$ denoting the investor's marginal utility. Further, under the assumption that the information contained in Ω_t is completely reflected by the state vector Z_t , the above condition implies that

$$E \left[U' \left(R_{p,t+1}(\alpha(Z_t; \beta)) \right) R_{t+1} \otimes Z_t \right] = 0, \quad (5)$$

with \otimes denoting element-by-element multiplication.

The above representation of the optimal asset allocation problem yields a testable representation that can be implemented using generalized method of moments (GMM) techniques (Hansen, 1982).

To make these theoretical results operational, we assume that the investor's utility function is isoelastic or CRRA and takes the following form:

$$U(R_{p,t+1}) = \frac{(1+R_{p,t+1})^{1-\gamma}}{1-\gamma}, \quad (6)$$

with γ being the investor's constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) coefficient. The choice of this family of utility functions is standard in portfolio theory problems and asset pricing; see Brandt (1999) and references therein.

The specification of the optimal portfolio allocated to the S&P 500 in (2) requires the choice of the state variables Z_t . In our setting we consider the above list of individual state variables used to create the tree-structured classifiers of the S&P 500 excess return and/or the three new binary state variables: $I_{CART,t}$, $I_{Bagging,t}$, and $I_{Random\ forest,t}$. To test the value added to the investor of the new binary state variables, we restrict the choice of the individual state variables to be the vector of the variables selected by the binary classifiers to classify each element of the sample D_t .

We evaluate different specifications of the optimal portfolio weight $\alpha_{S\&P500,t}$ or portfolio strategies by considering different investors' information sets. By doing so, we try to evaluate the added economic value of the binary classifiers. Thus, we consider:

a) A passive strategy that goes long in the S&P 500 ($\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = 1$) or a passive portfolio that invests 60% in the S&P 500 and 40% in the risk-free rate.

b) A benchmark strategy that considers the state variables vector used by the binary classifiers to classify each element of the sample, D_t : $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta D_t$.

c) A CART strategy that only includes the I_{CART} variable:
 $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{CART}} I_{CART,t}$.

d) A bagging strategy that only includes the $I_{Bagging}$ variable:
 $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{Bagging}} I_{Bagging,t}$.

e) A random-forest strategy that only includes the $I_{Random\ forest}$ variable:
 $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{Random\ Forest}} I_{Random\ Forest,t}$.

f) The I_{CART} variable and D_t strategy: $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{CART}} I_{CART,t} + \beta D_t$.

g) The $I_{Bagging}$ and D_t strategy: $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{Bagging}} I_{Bagging,t} + \beta D_t$.

h) The $I_{Random\ forest}$ and D_t strategy: $\alpha_{S\&P500,t} = \alpha + \beta_{I_{Random\ Forest}} I_{Random\ forest,t} + \beta D_t$.

(7)

2.3 Portfolio performance measures

We use the following metrics to measure the economic performance of the portfolios: 1) the main descriptive statistics of optimal excess portfolio return distribution: mean, volatility, skewness coefficient, and kurtosis, 2) the annualized Sharpe ratio, calculated as the mean portfolio excess return divided by the portfolio return volatility in annualized terms, and 3) the certainty equivalent return, CER. The CER is in this context a guaranteed return that makes the investor indifferent in expected terms between the risky portfolio $R_{p,t+1}$ and the riskless strategy of paying off CER. Under CRRA utility the CER is computed as:

$$CER = \left((1-\gamma) T^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^T U(1+R_{p,t+1}) \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} - 1. \quad (8)$$

3. Empirical results

This section commences by describing the data used in the empirical analysis and continues by presenting and discussing the empirical results obtained from the implementation of the tree-structured classifiers and the different optimal portfolio strategies introduced in the preceding sections. Thus, we first evaluate the accuracy of the competing tree-structured classifiers in predicting the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash in-sample and out-of-sample. We also discuss the most relevant variables uncovered by these tree-structured classifiers in predicting the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash, especially out-of-sample. The section continues by examining the added value to the investor from considering the new binary variables in the portfolio context.

3.1. Data description

Our data cover the period from June 1986 to June 2015. We collect monthly data from Bloomberg on the S&P 500, the CRB Industrial commodity index, the WTI oil prices, the VIX, and the three-month U.S. LIBOR interbank market interest rate. We also use the cyclically adjusted PER ratio from Robert Shiller's web page,⁸ which considers the ten-year moving average of real earnings. Furthermore, we collect the ten-year

⁸ <http://www.econ.yale.edu/~shiller/data.htm>

government bond yield, the three-month Treasury bill rate, and the yield of Moody's Baa- and Aaa-rated corporate bonds from the U.S. Federal Reserve.⁹ Finally, we collect the risk-free rate from the French database.¹⁰ Table 1 provides the main descriptive statistics of the state variables.

[Insert table 1 about here]

3.2. Tree-structured classifiers' in-sample and out-of-sample prediction of the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs cash. Which state variables matter?

In this section firstly we analyse the ability of the CART, bagging, and random-forest tree-structured classifiers to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash in-sample and out-of-sample using the above list of state variables. In our out-of-sample experiment, the binary classifiers are re-estimated every year using an expanding window of data until the end of the sample. The first binary classifier is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005. Then we consider the information available in period t , reflected in the values of the state variables, to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash at $t+1$ using the estimated binary classifiers. Therefore, the out-of-sample period covers 120 months. Secondly we characterize the in-sample homogeneous zones associated with the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash according to the CART to gain intuition about the role played by the state variables and their interactions to classify all the observations of our sample. Finally we select the most relevant state variables considered by the binary classifiers using the out-of-sample information.

Table 2 reports the accuracy of the different binary classifiers. The in-sample analysis reports remarkable accuracy that is always higher than 70%. The bagging and random-forest classifiers deliver outstanding accuracy of 88%, whereas the CART delivers lower overall accuracy of about 75%. However, the out-of-sample results show sensible deterioration of the accuracy results and remarkably report that the three methods deliver almost the same overall accuracy of about 70%. Therefore, we may conjecture that our sample and the choice of the state variables make the tree grown using the CART quite stable and negligible in relation to the gains of using more sophisticated models, like bagging and the random forest. This is in favour of the CART

⁹ <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econresdata/>

¹⁰ http://mba.tuck.dartmouth.edu/pages/faculty/ken.french/data_library.html

method, as its interpretation is always more appealing and intuitive than that of the bagging and random-forest methods.

[Insert table 2 about here]

Figure 1 plots the classification tree grown from the CART using the entire sample. The classification tree is simple and contains five terminal nodes and four levels of partitioning. The state variable appearing in the root node is the VIX momentum. There are two homogeneous zones associated with the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash. First, if we observe in period t that the VIX momentum is below 0.28 (mainly negative) and the detrended risk-free rate is larger than -0.34, then we expect that the S&P 500 will outperform the cash in period $t+1$. The first homogeneous zone reflects that decreasing uncertainty and market risk aversion and a detrended risk-free rate above a threshold are associated with greater attractiveness of the stock market vs. the cash. Second, if we observe in period t that the VIX momentum is above 0.28, the level of the VIX is below 22%, and the EYBY momentum is larger than -0.018, then we also expect that the S&P 500 will outperform the cash in period $t+1$. The second homogeneous zone reflects that periods characterized by increasing uncertainty and market risk aversion, as measured by a VIX momentum higher than a positive threshold, are still compatible with greater attractiveness of the stock market vs. cash if the volatility is below 22% or, alternatively, we are not in a high volatility state, and the EYBY momentum is larger than a threshold that is usually linked to recent underperformance of the stock market vs. the bond market that may reverse.

[Insert figure 1 about here]

The tree only considers 4 state variables from the list of 18 state variables to classify the in-sample data: the VIX momentum, VIX level, detrended risk-free rate, and EYBY momentum. Therefore, the in-sample analysis shows that a state variable that captures the investor fear gauge or the market sentiment and its dynamics, VIX level and momentum, a measure of the relative stock market valuation dynamics, EYBY momentum, and a measure of the interest rate dynamics, the detrended risk-free rate, contains the relevant information to predict the behaviour of the performance of the

S&P 500 vs. cash. It is interesting to outline that the state variables' momentum plays a key role and that the tree has a structure that fits the intuition.

Table 3 reports the state variables selected by the CART in the out-of-sample period. The stability of the choice of the state variables in the out-of-sample period is remarkable, which reinforces the idea that the CART may be quite stable in our sample. Figures 2 and 3 show the out-of-sample state variables' importance calculated from the out-of-bag observations (Breiman, 1996c) using bagging and the random forest. For any variable this measure is the increase in prediction error if the values of that variable are permuted across the out-of-bag observations. This measure is computed for every tree then averaged over the entire ensemble and divided by the standard deviation over the entire ensemble. Both tree-structured classifiers display a high level of importance linked to the variables chosen by the CART (the VIX level and momentum, detrended risk-free rate, and EYBY momentum) and provide a relevant role to the EYBY level. Hereafter we consider this vector of five state variables to evaluate the added economic value of the three new binary state variables: $I_{CART,t}$, $I_{Bagging,t}$, and $I_{Random\ forest,t}$. Therefore, the vector $D_t=[VIX, VIX\ momentum, EYBY, EYBY\ momentum, detrended\ risk-free\ rate]$.

[Insert table 3 about here]

3.3. Optimal portfolio and added economic value of tree-structured classifiers' prediction

In this section we present the in-sample and out-of-sample optimal portfolio estimated (2) using the different specifications considered in (7). We also report the in-sample and out-of-sample added economic value of considering the binary state variables in the resolution of the investor's asset allocation problem.

3.3.1 Optimal portfolio choice

Table 4 presents the in-sample parameter estimates optimized for the power utility function defined by the CRRA parameter γ , equal to 10. The results confirm that the optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is positively and very significantly related to the new binary state variables considered separately and in isolation, I_{CART} , $I_{Bagging}$, and $I_{Random\ forest}$ (see 7.c, 7.d, and 7.e). As expected, if the binary state variable, regardless of

the method used, takes the value one and the S&P 500 is expected to outperform the cash, this is a strong signal of the attractiveness of the stock market for the investor. The strength of the signal of going long in the S&P 500, measured by the corresponding value β , is even larger for the bagging and random-forest binary variables, as the degree of accuracy of these models is higher than that of the CART in-sample. The specification that only considers the state variables vector D_t (see 7.b) also shows that the optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is negatively related to the VIX level and momentum and positively related to the EYBY. These results are intuitive in a linear setting. High values of the VIX and their recent increases are associated with increases in the financial market uncertainty and upsurges in the discount rates used by the investors that would reduce the attractiveness of the S&P 500 vs. cash in the short term. Conversely, a high value of the EYBY can increase the likelihood of an undervalued stock market and the attractiveness of the S&P 500 vs. cash. Interestingly, the optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is not significantly related either to the detrended risk-free rate or to the EYBY momentum, which were selected as important state variables by the tree-structured classifiers. Table 4 also reports that jointly considering the state variables vector D_t and the binary variables has a very significant impact on the relationship between the state variables and the optimal portfolio allocation to the S&P 500. Only the binary state variables are positively and significantly related to the optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500, and none of the variables belonging to the state variables vector D_t are significant, with the exception of the detrended risk-free rate considered with I_{CART} . Therefore, we can conclude that the information embedded in the binary variables is superior to the isolated state variables' information due to its ability to reflect the non-linearities governing the interaction of the state variables.

[Insert table 4 about here]

Table 5 reports the out-of-sample estimates. The out-of-sample estimates and t -statistics are the time series average from each out-of-sample estimation of the optimal portfolio policy. The first optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005, and after this the model is re-estimated for every year using an expanding window of data until the end of the sample. Therefore, the out-of-sample period covers 120 months. The most relevant conclusion is that the in-sample

results are still valid out-of-sample. Thus, investors should mainly consider the information embedded in the binary state variables to time the stock market.

[Insert table 5 about here]

3.3.2 Economic value of the binary state variables: I_{CART} , $I_{Bagging}$, and $I_{Random forest}$

Tables 7 and 8 present the in-sample and out-of-sample performance of the optimal portfolio given the different specifications considered, displaying the portfolio return statistics: the average return, standard deviation and Sharpe ratio of returns, skewness coefficient, kurtosis, and certainty equivalent return. We also report the in-sample and out-of-sample performance of the passive strategies represented by investing 100% or 60% in the S&P 500. We present the results assuming that short positions are ruled out, limiting the optimal portfolio leverage.

Table 7 reports the in-sample results, and, as expected, the in-sample optimal portfolios that do not consider a constant investor's information set deliver certainty equivalent return gains and a higher Sharpe ratio than the passive strategies, with a positive skewness coefficient and usually lower kurtosis. The buy–hold strategy generates an average return of 0.35% and 0.49% per month, leading to an annualized Sharpe ratio of 0.33. The return distribution of the passive strategies is slightly biased towards negative returns (negative skewness) and has fatter tails than normal (kurtosis larger than 6). The optimal strategy that only considers the state variables selected by the tree-structured classifiers generates an average return of 0.92% per month, which leads to an annualized Sharpe ratio of 1.32. The return distribution of the passive strategies is slightly biased towards positive returns (skewness equal to 0.33) and has thinner tails than normal (kurtosis lower than 3). The annualized certainty equivalent return gain compared with the passive strategies is very significant, always attaining values larger than 10%. These impressive results are still improved if we consider the in-sample optimal portfolios formed on the basis of the binary state variables, I_{CART} , $I_{Bagging}$, and $I_{Random forest}$, considered in isolation or combined with D_t . These portfolios provide a certainty equivalent return gain and a higher Sharpe ratio than the strategy that only considers the state variables vector D_t . The increase in the Sharpe ratio from using these models is larger than 40%, reaching outstanding values close to 2; the annualized

certainty equivalent return gain is very significant in always attaining values larger than 3%. The best in-sample models correspond to the models that include the binary state variables $I_{Bagging}$ and $I_{Random\ forest}$. This in-sample result emanates from the greater accuracy in predicting the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash shown by the bagging and random-forest methods.

Table 8 also reports that out-of-sample optimal portfolios deliver a certainty equivalent return gain and larger Sharpe ratio than the passive strategies, with a larger skewness coefficient and usually lower kurtosis but with sensible deterioration. Within the optimized strategies, we again find that the optimal portfolios formed on the basis of the binary state variables, I_{CART} , $I_{Bagging}$, and $I_{Random\ forest}$, considered in isolation or combined with D_t , provide a higher certainty equivalent return and Sharpe ratio than the strategy that only considers the state variables vector D_t . The increase in the Sharpe ratio from using these models still reaches remarkable values that are always higher than 1.2 vs. 1.07 attained by the model that excludes the binary state variables; the certainty equivalent return gain is again very significant, always attaining values larger than 1%, compared with the model that excludes the binary state variables. The main difference between the in-sample and the out-of-sample results is that the best out-of-sample models correspond to the models that include the binary state variables I_{CART} and $I_{Bagging}$. This out-of-sample result is compatible with the greater accuracy in predicting the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash shown by the CART and bagging methods.

4. Conclusion

The high level of complexity of the financial markets makes the use of tree-structured classifiers interesting, because they can handle problems with many state variables that are likely to be subject to non-linearities and/or structural breaks in their relationship with the asset returns. In this paper we consider the ability of the CART and more refined alternatives, like bagging and the random forest, to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash using the state variables considered by the return predictability literature. The investor welfare gain of investing according to the signal provided by the new binary state variables created is especially significant in terms of the Sharpe ratio and certainty equivalent return increases even out-of-sample. Interestingly, bagging and

the random forest do not improve the CART performance in our sample, pointing out the stability of the CART in our sample.

Our future agenda is concerned with the comparison of the CART methodology with other non-parametric non-linear models, such as neural networks, or parametric non-linear models, like the Markov regime-switching models (Hamilton, 1989).

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Table 1: Description of the state variables considered by the binary classifiers

Level	Mean	STD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Detrended risk-free rate	-0.06	0.47	-0.69	4.34
Term spread	13.75	30.38	3.41	16.53
Default spread	0.97	0.39	3.09	16.53
Robert Shiller PER	24.17	7.13	0.99	3.70
Robert Shiller earning yield bond yield	1.00	0.57	1.63	5.11
VIX	20.75	8.43	1.70	7.38
Three-month CRB industrial commodity index return	0.82	5.74	-0.58	7.02
Three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation	2.71	17.20	0.68	8.12
U.S. Ted spread	0.59	0.44	1.63	6.35
Momentum	Mean	STD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Detrended risk-free rate	0.00	0.26	-0.06	5.84
Term spread	0.56	16.17	-1.02	30.50
Default spread	0.00	0.16	1.34	22.45
Robert Shiller PER	0.08	1.23	-0.80	5.32
Robert Shiller earning yield bond yield	0.00	0.16	1.57	15.74
VIX	-0.02	5.58	2.17	15.42
Three-month CRB industrial commodity index return	-0.01	4.85	0.41	4.69
Three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation	0.12	17.39	0.18	7.64
U.S. Ted spread	0.00	0.25	0.92	15.11

The table reports the mean, standard deviation (STD), skewness coefficient, and kurtosis of the level and three-month momentum of the following state variables: the detrended risk-free rate; the term spread, measured as the ratio between the ten-year government bond yield and the three-month Treasury bill rate; the default spread or U.S. credit spread, defined as the yield difference between Moody's Baa-rated and Moody's Aaa-rated corporate bonds; the Robert Shiller price to earnings ratio (PER) and the Robert Shiller earning yield bond yield (EYBY); the VIX; the three-month CRB industrial commodity index return; the three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation; and the U.S. Ted spread, measured as the difference between the three-month U.S. LIBOR interbank market interest rate and the three-month U.S. Treasury bill rate.

Table 2: Classification accuracy of different binary classifiers

Method	Accuracy					
	In-sample			Out-of-sample		
	S&P 500 outperformance	S&P 500 underperformance	Total	S&P 500 outperformance	S&P 500 underperformance	Total
<i>CART</i>	81.19%	65.73%	74.78%	85.90%	40.48%	70%
<i>Bagging</i>	91.58%	83.22%	88.12%	85.90%	47.62%	72.50%
<i>Random forest</i>	93.07%	81.12%	88.12%	89.74%	30.95%	69.17%

The table reports the accuracy of the binary classifiers' prediction of the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash in-sample and out-of-sample. These binary classifiers consider the following explanatory variables: the detrended risk-free rate; the term spread, measured as the ratio between the ten-year government bond yield and the three-month Treasury bill rate; the default spread or U.S. credit spread, defined as the yield difference between Moody's Baa-rated and Moody's Aaa-rated corporate bonds; the Robert Shiller price to earnings ratio (PER) and the Robert Shiller earning yield bond yield (EYBY); the VIX; the three-month CRB industrial commodity index return; and the three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation and the U.S. Ted spread, measured as the difference between the three-month U.S. LIBOR interbank market interest rate and the three-month U.S. Treasury bill rate. The sample data cover the period from June 1986 to June 2015. In the out-of-sample exercise, the first binary classifier is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005. Then we consider the information available in period t , reflected in the values of the state variables, to predict the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash in $t+1$ using the estimated binary classifiers. Therefore, the out-of-sample period covers 120 months. In our application $B=200$ and the number of variables considered by the random forest equals $18^{1/2}$.

Table 3: State variables appearing in the out-of-sample classification trees grown from the CART

Period 1986–2005	Period 1986–2006	Period 1986–2007	Period 1986–2008	Period 1986–2009	Period 1986–2010	Period 1986–2011	Period 1986–2012	Period 1986–2013	Period 1986–2014
VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum	VIX momentum
Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate	Detrended risk-free rate
-	-	-	VIX	VIX	VIX	VIX	VIX	VIX	
-	-	-	EYBY momentum	EYBY momentum	EYBY momentum	EYBY momentum	EYBY momentum	EYBY momentum	
-	-	-	Robert Shiller PER momentum		U.S. Ted spread momentum	U.S. Ted spread momentum			

The table reports the state variables that the CART considers in the out-of-sample period. In our out-of-sample experiment, the binary classifiers are re-estimated every year using an expanding window of data until the end of the sample. The first binary classifier is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005.

Table 4: Simple linear portfolio policy. In-sample results

Variable	All variables strategy	CART strategy	Bagging strategy	Random-forest strategy	CART strategy+all variables	Bagging strategy+all variables	Random-forest strategy+all variables
A	2.05	-1.00	-2.80	-3.42	-1.49	-4.00	-6.42
t -stat	(3.45)	(-3.58)	(-4.93)	(-4.73)	(-1.56)	(-2.86)	(-4.38)
$\beta_{I\text{CART}}$		3.18			3.34		
t -stat		(5.91)			(4.63)		
$\beta_{I\text{Bagging}}$			6.66			7.47	
t -stat			(8.04)			(7.59)	
$\beta_{I\text{RForest}}$				6.04			6.66
t -stat				(6.65)			(6.67)
β_{VIX}	-0.10				-0.03	0.02	0.07
t -stat	(-4.27)				(-0.86)	(0.41)	(1.68)
$\beta_{VIX\text{Mom}}$	-0.19				-0.11	0.04	-0.01
t -stat	(-3.73)				(-1.94)	(0.73)	(-0.29)
β_{EYBY}	1.01				0.89	0.12	1.20
t -stat	(2.94)				(1.89)	(0.20)	(1.82)
$\beta_{EYBY\text{Mom}}$	-0.02				-1.55	-1.98	-3.38
t -stat	(-0.01)				(-0.83)	(-0.79)	(-1.43)
$\beta_{RF\text{detrended}}$	0.21				-1.03	-1.33	0.46
t -stat	(0.61)				(-2.00)	(-1.66)	(0.67)

This table shows the in-sample estimates of the optimal portfolio weight allocated to the S&P 500 specified in equation (2) and optimized for a power utility function with CRRA $\gamma=10$. The sample data cover the period from June 1986 to June 2015. We consider the strategies b to h in (7).

Table 5: Simple linear portfolio policy. Out-of-sample results

Variable	All variables strategy	CART strategy	Bagging strategy	Random-forest strategy	CART strategy+all variables	Bagging strategy+all variables	Random-forest strategy+all variables
α	1.48	-1.08	-3.43	-4.12	-1.07	-8.39	-10.75
t -stat	(1.87)	(-3.18)	(-4.52)	(-4.41)	(-0.85)	(-3.57)	(-4.41)
$\beta_{I\text{CART}}$		3.07			2.85		
t -stat		(5.68)			(4.09)		
$\beta_{I\text{Bagging}}$			7.84			10.12	
t -stat			(7.54)			(7.98)	
$\beta_{I\text{RForest}}$				9.07			12.49
t -stat				(7.26)			(7.67)
β_{VIX}	-0.09				-0.05	0.10	0.20
t -stat	(-2.58)				(-1.17)	(1.41)	(2.52)
$\beta_{VIX\text{Mom}}$	-0.25				-0.10	0.02	-0.03
t -stat	(-3.69)				(-1.22)	(0.42)	(-0.45)
β_{EYBY}	1.59				1.62	1.73	0.22
t -stat	(1.77)				(1.31)	(0.40)	(-0.19)
$\beta_{EYBY\text{Mom}}$	-0.02				-1.13	-17.69	-15.16
t -stat	(-0.01)				(-0.12)	(-2.07)	(-1.40)
$\beta_{RF\text{ detrended}}$	0.22				-0.38	-1.16	-0.51
t -stat	(0.61)				(-0.69)	(-1.33)	(-0.45)

This table shows the out-of-sample estimates of the optimal portfolio weight allocated to the S&P 500 specified in equation (2) and optimized for a power utility function with CRRA $\gamma=10$. The sample data cover the period from June 1986 to June 2015. We consider the strategies b to h in (7). The out-of-sample estimates and t-statistics are the time series average from each out-of-sample estimation of the optimal portfolio policy. The first optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005, and after this the model is re-estimated for every year using an expanding window of data until the end of the sample.

Table 6: Investment performance of the optimized strategies in-sample

Variable	S&P 500	Passive strategy	All variables strategy	CART strategy	Bagging strategy	Random-forest strategy	CART strategy+all variables	Bagging strategy+all variables	Random-forest strategy+all variables
μ	0.35%	0.49%	0.92%	1.19%	1.34%	1.35%	1.28%	1.40%	1.37%
σ	3.68%	2.21%	2.41%	2.13%	2.11%	2.12%	2.20%	2.19%	2.11%
Sharpe ratio	0.33	0.33	1.32	1.93	2.19	2.21	2.02	2.22	2.44
Skewness coefficient	-1.40	-1.41	0.33	0.56	1.24	0.82	0.40	1.25	0.82
Kurtosis	6.06	6.13	2.06	3.72	3.55	14.36	3.15	3.43	4.37
<i>CER</i>	-3.38%	2.51%	9.68%	12.69%	16.64%	16.57%	13.04%	16.86%	16.63%

This table shows the economic value of the in-sample portfolio weight allocated to the S&P 500 specified in equation (2) and optimized for a power utility function with a CRRA coefficient ($\gamma=10$). μ is the monthly S&P 500 excess return mean, σ is the monthly S&P 500 excess return volatility, the Sharpe ratio is in annualized terms, and CER is the certainty equivalent return in annualized terms.

Table 7: Investment performance of the optimized strategies out-of-sample

Variable	S&P 500	Passive strategy	All variables strategy	CART strategy	Bagging strategy	Random-forest strategy	CART strategy+all variables	Bagging strategy+all variables	Random-forest strategy+all variables
μ	0.35%	0.32%	0.85%	1.18%	0.95%	0.92%	1.09%	1.10%	0.89%
σ	3.97%	2.37%	2.75%	2.72%	2.48%	2.63%	2.63%	2.45%	2.35%
Sharpe ratio	0.31	0.31	1.07	1.51	1.32	1.21	1.44	1.56	1.30
Skewness coefficient	-2.05	-2.10	-0.19	-0.08	0.13	-0.07	-0.14	0.41	-0.57
Kurtosis	9.85	9.99	2.30	2.05	3.48	2.77	2.64	2.87	1.85
<i>CER</i>	-9.38%	-0.34%	6.94%	11.10%	9.03%	8.20%	10.28%	11.09%	8.52%

This table shows the economic value of the out-of-sample portfolio weight allocated to the S&P 500 specified in equation (2) and optimized for a power utility function with a CRRA coefficient ($\gamma=10$). μ is the monthly S&P 500 excess return mean, σ is the monthly S&P 500 excess return volatility, the Sharpe ratio is in annualized terms, and CER is the certainty equivalent return in annualized terms. The first optimal weight allocated to the S&P 500 is estimated with data from June 1986 to June 2005, and after this the model is re-estimated for every year using an expanding window of data until the end of the sample.

Figure 1: CART of the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash

The figure plots the CART of the outperformance of the S&P 500 vs. cash based on the following state variables: the detrended risk-free rate; the term spread, measured as the ratio between the ten-year government bond yield and the three-month Treasury bill rate; the default spread or U.S. credit spread, defined as the yield difference between Moody’s Baa-rated and Moody’s Aaa-rated corporate bonds; the Robert Shiller price to earnings ratio (PER) and the Robert Shiller earning yield bond yield (EYBY); the VIX; the three-month CRB industrial commodity index return; and the three-month West Texas Intermediate oil price variation and the U.S. Ted spread, measured as the difference between the three-month U.S. LIBOR interbank market interest rate and the three-month U.S. Treasury bill rate. The sample data cover the period from June 1986 to June 2015.

Figure 2: Out-of-sample state variables' importance. Bagging and the random forest

The figure shows, for every year of the out-of-sample period, the state variables' importance calculated from the out-of-bag observations using bagging and the random forest. For any variable this measure is the increase in the classification error if the values of that variable are permuted across the out-of-bag observations. This measure is computed for every tree then averaged over the entire ensemble and divided by the standard deviation over the entire ensemble.